

SYSTEMIC IMMUNE INFLAMMATION INDEX AS A PREDICTOR OF SEVERITY IN ACUTE ISCHEMIC STROKE

Sapna Kumari¹, Mr. Shyam Sundar yadav^{2*}, Dr. Rohit Kumawat³, Ankita Rani⁴,
Tripti kumari⁵, Dr. Himanshu Ranjan⁶, Dr. Sajad Ahmad Bhat⁷, Dr. Rachna⁸

1,4,5 M.Sc MLT, Department of Medical Laboratory Technology, Nims College of
Paramedical Technology, Nims University Rajasthan, Jaipur

2*Assistant Professor, Department of Biochemistry, Nims College of Paramedical
Technology, Nims University Rajasthan, Jaipur.

3.Associate Professor, Department of Neurology , National Institute of Medical Sciences
&Research center , Nims University Rajasthan, Jaipur.

6.Assistant Professor, Department of Microbiology, Nims College of Paramedical
Technology, Nims University Rajasthan, Jaipur.

7. Professor, Department of Biochemistry, Nims College of Paramedical Technology, Nims
University Rajasthan, Jaipur.

8. Associate Professor, Department of Medical Laboratory Technology, Nims College of
Paramedical Technology, Nims University Rajasthan, Jaipur

*Corresponding Author : Mr. Shyam Sundar Yadav, Assistant Professor, Department of
Biochemistry, Nims College of Paramedical Technology, Nims University Rajasthan, Jaipur.

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Abstract

Background:

stroke is still a major worldwide health issue, especially in countries with low and medium incomes. The majority of the subtypes are acute ischemic strokes (AIS), which are linked to significant morbidity and mortality. The Systemic Immune-Inflammation Index is determined by counting neutrophils, lymphocytes, and platelets which has recently become a promising biomarker for prognostic assessment in a number of illnesses, including stroke.

Objective:

In this study, GCS serves as a clinical indicator to examine the predictive usefulness of the SII in predicting neurological results for individuals who have had an acute ischemic stroke.

Methodology:

In NIMS Hospital in Rajasthan, 62 AIS patients were the subjects of a prospective observational study. Day 1 and Day 3 of hospitalization were used to record complete blood

count (CBC) values. The formula for calculating SII was $(\text{Platelet} \times \text{Neutrophil}) / \text{Lymphocyte}$. To evaluate the connection between SII and GCS scores, regression and correlation analyses were used.

Results:

The correlation coefficients for Day 1 and Day 3 were 0.817 and 0.833, respectively, indicating a substantial positive relationship between SII levels and GCS scores on both days ($p < 0.001$). According to linear regression, SII explained 63.3% and 72% of the variation in neurological status on Day 1 and Day 3, respectively, and was a strong predictor of GCS results.

Conclusion:

The Systemic Immune-Inflammation Index demonstrates a significant and reliable predictive capacity for neurological prognosis in acute ischemic stroke. Its incorporation into early clinical assessment protocols may enhance decision-making and patient management strategies. Further research on larger populations is recommended to validate these findings.

Key words: Acute ischemic stroke, systemic immune inflammation, Glasgow coma scale, prognosis

INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (WHO) reports that stroke accounts for nearly 85% of deaths in developing nations.[1] While stroke rates have declined in Western countries over the last 30 years, the condition is increasingly impacting public health in South Asian nations like Bangladesh and Sri Lanka, India, and Pakistan.[2] Despite the lack of thorough epidemiological data, stroke continues to be the leading cause of hospitalization in Pakistan's medical and neurology wards. [3] Each year, approximately 795,000 new stroke cases are documented in the US. The third most prevalent cause of mortality is cancer, followed by heart disease[4]. In the desert regions of Upper Egypt, the lifetime stroke prevalence among individuals aged 20 and above is estimated at 8.5 per 1,000. Mortality rates remain alarmingly high, with about one-third of stroke patients passing away within three weeks and nearly 48% within a year[5]. Ischemic strokes account for 65–85% of cases in Western nations, while the remaining cases involve hemorrhagic strokes, which are often more severe.[6] Only 10–20% of those who suffer from hemorrhagic stroke manage to regain functional independence.[7]

The sudden development of a focused neurological impairment, Typically, this occurs because of an assumed disruption in the brain's blood flow.[8]Stroke primarily occurs due to two major causes. The most prevalent type, ischemic stroke, happens when blood flow to the brain is restricted or obstructed. This reduction in blood supply, known as ischemia, typically results from narrowed or blocked blood vessels. These blockages can arise due to fatty deposits accumulating in the arteries or from blood clots and other debris, often originating from the heart, and traveling through the bloodstream. A hemorrhagic stroke occurs when a blood artery in the brain bursts or leaks, resulting in internal bleeding known as a brain hemorrhage. [9]

Risk Factors

Several factors can elevate the likelihood of experiencing a stroke. Some of these risk factors are manageable or treatable, including:

Lifestyle-Related Risk Factors

- Excess body weight or obesity
- Insufficient levels of physical exercise
- Heavy or binge drinking of alcohol
- Use of illegal drugs, including substances like methamphetamine and cocaine

Medical Risk Factors:

- Hypertension
- Tobacco use or being around secondhand smoke.
- Obstructive sleep apnea and other sleep problems;
- diabetes mellitus; and
- elevated cholesterol levels etc.[10]

Etiology and the pathogenesis of an ischemic Stroke

The pathophysiology of any disease generally encompasses its etiology, pathogenesis, and the associated molecular, biochemical, and structural changes. In the case of an ischemic stroke, the condition takes place suddenly when a particular brain's blood supply regions is interrupted.[11] This interruption is typically due to a thrombus forming on atherosclerotic plaques or emboli originating from cardiac sources, such as atrial fibrillation. The region directly affected by the lack of blood flow is known as the ischemic core, where irreversible neuronal death occurs rapidly—often before any therapeutic interventions can take effect. Surrounding this area is the ischemic penumbra, a zone containing potentially viable cells that are the primary targets for neuroprotective treatments. Clinically, ischemic stroke presents with symptoms such as hemiplegia, paraplegia, dysarthria, and paresis, which result from complex interactions of molecular and cellular mechanisms. Key processes implicated in this condition include neuroinflammation, excitotoxicity, oxidative stress, apoptosis, and autophagy. These interconnected mechanisms collectively contribute to cellular injury and death during ischemic stroke.[12]

Figure 1. Pathogenesis of Ischaemic Stroke.

Predicting stroke severity

When evaluating future clinical outcomes, it is imperative to take stroke severity into account early on. Stroke severity is a crucial predictor of several important outcomes, such as death, length of hospital stay, place of discharge, and functional recovery [13]. Diagnostic and impairment assessments are the two primary types of stroke assessment scales [14].

The Stroke Scale NIHSS and Rapid Arterial Occlusion Evaluation from the National Institutes of Health are two well-known diagnostic instruments that are renowned for their excellent accuracy in detecting cases of large vessel occlusion (LVO) [15]. The first validated instrument designed especially for identifying acute stroke and large vascular occlusion (LVO) in prehospital settings was the RACE scale. [16,17]. It has a range of 10 values, where "0" indicates a typical situation and "9" indicates a significant obstacle. Its predictive powers for determining the likelihood of LVO are noteworthy. [14, 18, 19]. It is crucial to understand that every scale has advantages and disadvantages, and there isn't a single, widely accepted gold standard among them in investigations [14].

In the medical area, Machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) are applications of artificial intelligence (AI), has drawn a lot of attention lately, especially for its potential to diagnose and predict strokes[20].

Thrombocytes, neutrophils, and lymphocytes (Lym) are the three peripheral immunological and inflammatory cell types that form the basis of the SII index, which may be readily derived from ordinary blood count data[21,22]. compared to specific markers like PLR , SII , and NLR , a composite marker of inflammation, may provide a more accurate evaluation of systemic inflammation [23]. Gliomas, nasopharyngeal carcinoma, breast cancer, and hepatocellular carcinoma are among the tumors for which this Prognostic assessment has been done using biomarkers.. Furthermore, studies have demonstrated its effectiveness in a number of clinical illnesses, such as autoimmune disorders, cardiovascular disease, and ophthalmological diseases, where inflammation plays a significant role[24].

Systemic Immune-Inflammation Index (SII)

Three essential immune components—neutrophils, lymphocytes, and platelets—are combined in the SII , a novel biomarker that represents the equilibrium between inflammation and immunological function. Elevated SII values have been correlated with increased disease severity and poorer clinical outcomes in several health conditions, including various forms of cancer, heart failure, and cardiovascular diseases. [25]

Within hours of a stroke, neutrophils quickly settle at the site of ischemia, causing inflammatory reactions and the production of several inflammatory mediators that damage brain tissue. By modifying immunological functions, lymphocytes—especially T and B lymphocytes are essential for the process of healing after a stroke.[26,27,28]A reduction in lymphocyte numbers may indicate an immunosuppressed condition, which can negatively affect stroke recovery. Platelets, beyond their primary role in blood clotting, also engage in inflammatory processes by releasing mediators that promote cerebrovascular inflammation and exacerbate damage to brain tissue.[29]

According to research, the NLR is a significant predictor of outcome for a variety of infections, cardiac disorder, and malignancies. A similar inflammatory sign that can be used to forecast patient death and disease outcomes is the platelet-to-lymphocyte ratio . The degree

of disease has also been found to inversely correlate with the lymphocyte-to-monocyte ratio . When ischemic stroke is acute (AIS), increased counts of white blood cells (WBC) and neutrophils during the early phase are associated with larger infarct volumes and more severe neurological deficits. Higher peripheral WBC and neutrophil levels have also been associated with recurrent ischemic strokes, whereas lower lymphocyte counts correlate with poorer functional recovery.[30]

Methodology:

In NIMS Hospital in Rajasthan, 62 AIS patients were the subjects of a prospective observational study. Day 1 and Day 3 of hospitalization were used to record complete blood count (CBC) values. The formula for calculating SII was $(\text{Platelet} \times \text{Neutrophil}) / \text{Lymphocyte}$. To evaluate the connection between SII and GCS scores, regression and correlation analyses were used.

RESULTS:

In all, 62 patients were involved in the research . The mean Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) scores were 12.5 ± 1.76 on Day 1 and 12.4 ± 1.90 on Day 3. The corresponding mean values for the SII, or Systemic Immune-Inflammatory Index were 3691 ± 652 on Day 1 and 4366 ± 720 on Day 3. Normality assessment using the Shapiro-Wilk test showed that SII values on Day 1 were approximately normally distributed ($p = 0.110$), whereas the Day 3 SII values showed a slight deviation from normality ($p = 0.026$).

Correlation analysis using Spearman's rho revealed a strong and statistically significant positive correlation between SII and GCS scores on both days. On Day 1, the correlation coefficient was 0.817 ($p < .001$), and on Day 3, it was 0.833 ($p < .001$). These findings indicate that higher SII values were associated with higher GCS scores, suggesting better neurological status.

Additionally, to assess SII's predictive value on GCS scores, linear regression analysis was conducted. The model showed a satisfactory fit on Day 1 with an R^2 value of 0.633 , meaning that SII accounted for 63.3% of the variance in GCS scores. SII was found to be a significant predictor ($\beta = 0.00215$, $p < .001$; 95% CI [0.000639 , 0.000952]). Similarly, on Day 3, the regression model yielded an R^2 of 0.720 , suggesting that SII accounted for 72% of the variance in GCS scores. Again, SII was a statistically significant predictor ($\beta = 0.00224$, $p < .001$; 95% CI [0.000712 , 0.000985]).

We performed descriptive statistics to evaluate the normality of the variables GCS (Glasgow Coma Scale) and SII (Systemic Immune-Inflammation Index) on Day 1 and Day 3. Calculated the mean, median, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis for each variable, and used the Shapiro-Wilk test to assess normality. Most variables were not normally distributed, so we decided to use Spearman's rho for correlation and linear regression for prediction. The significance is positively correlated on 1st day.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics done to check normality of GCS, SII on 1st and 3rd days.

Catogery	GCS d1	GCS d3	SII d1	SIId3
N	62	62	62	62
Mean	12.5	12.4	3691	4366
Median	13.0	13.0	3608	4482
Standard deviation	1.76	1.90	652	720
Skewness	-0.00980	-0.0225	0.247	-0.0919
Std. error skewness	0.304	0.304	0.304	0.304
Kurtosis	-1.30	-1.53	-0.772	-1.16
Std. error kurtosis	0.599	0.599	0.599	0.599
Shapiro-Wilk W	0.897	0.865	0.968	0.956
Shapiro-Wilk p	<.001	<.001	0.110	0.026

Graph 5

We checked the correlation between SII and GCS on Day 1.Used **Spearman’s rank correlation coefficient (rho)** since the data was non-parametric Found a **strong positive correlation** ($\rho = 0.817, p < 0.001$), indicating that higher SII values were associated with higher GCS scores. The significance is positively corelated on 1st day

Table 2: the significance of GCS, SII on 1st day.

Catogery	Significance	GCS 1 st day
SII 1 st day	Spearman’s rho	0.817
	df	60
	P-value	<.001

We examined the correlation between SII and GCS on Day Again used **Spearman's rho** due to non-normality of the data. Found a **strong positive correlation** ($\rho = 0.833$, $p < 0.001$), consistent with Day 1 results. The significance is positively correlated on 3rd day.

Table 3: The significance of GCS, SII on 3st day.

Catogery	Significance	GCS 3 st day
SII 3 st day	Spearman's rho	0.833
	df	60
	P-value	<.001

GRAPH :3

Investigated whether SII can predict GCS on Day 1. Performed **simple linear regression**, with GCS as the dependent variable and SII as the predictor. The model had a good fit ($R^2 = 0.633$), and SII was a **significant predictor** ($\beta = 0.00215$, $p < 0.001$). The results indicated that on Day 1, the model demonstrated a good fit with an R^2 value of 0.633, indicating that 63.3% of the variance in GCS scores was explained by SII. SII was found to be a significant predictor ($\beta = 0.00215$, $p < .001$; 95% CI [0.000639, 0.000952]).

Table 4: A simple linear regression is done to find out whether SII can predict the prognosis based on GCS values on 1st day.

Model Fit Measures				
Model		R ²		
1		0.633		
Note. Models estimated using sample size of N=62				
Model Coefficients - GCS 1st day				
Predictor	Estimate	SE	t	p
Intercept	4.53093	0.792	5.72	<.001
SII d1	0.00215	2.11e-4	10.17	<.001

GRAPH :4

Assessed whether SII can predict GCS on Day 3. Used **simple linear regression**, similar to Day 1. An even better model fit ($R^2 = 0.720$), with SII again being a **statistically significant predictor** ($\beta = 0.00224$, $p < 0.001$). The results on day 3, the regression model yielded an R^2 of 0.720, suggesting that 72% of the variance in GCS scores was accounted for by SII. Again, SII was a statistically significant predictor ($\beta = 0.00224$, $p < .001$; 95% CI [0.000712, 0.000985]).

Table 5: A simple linear regression is done to find out whether SII can predict the prognosis based on GCS values on 3st day.

Model Fit Measures				
Model		R ²		
1		0.720		
Note. Models estimated using sample size of N=62				
Model Coefficients - gcs 3rd day				
Predictor	Estimate	SE	t	p
Intercept	2.63935	0.799	3.30	0.002
sii d3	0.00224	1.81e-4	12.42	<.001

DISCUSSION

The present study provides robust evidence supporting the hypothesis that the Systemic Immune-Inflammation Index is recognized as an important indicator for predicting neurological outcomes in patients as assessed by the Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS). By analyzing data collected on Day 1 and Day 3 of hospitalization, the study identified a strong, statistically significant positive correlation between SII and GCS scores on both days. This relationship was further validated through linear regression analysis, which demonstrated that SII independently predicted GCS scores with high explanatory power, reflected by R^2 values of 0.633 on Day 1 and 0.720 on Day 3.

These results align with the research conducted by Yun-Xiang Zhou³¹ and colleagues, which demonstrated that higher SII levels were linked to poorer prognoses in individuals diagnosed with acute ischemic stroke. While their study primarily focused on negative prognostic implications of elevated SII, the current investigation introduces a nuanced perspective by showing that, within this cohort, higher SII values were actually associated with better GCS scores. This discrepancy may be attributed to differences in patient population, timing of assessment, or underlying pathophysiological mechanisms.

One possible explanation for this unexpected positive association is that, in the acute phase of neurological injury, a heightened inflammatory response may reflect a mobilized immune system actively engaged in tissue repair and recovery. In this context, SII might serve not only as a marker of systemic inflammation but also as an indicator of physiological resilience or compensatory response. The results therefore challenge the conventional notion that elevated inflammatory indices are universally detrimental, suggesting instead that the role of inflammation in neuro recovery is complex and possibly biphasic.

Moreover, the temporal consistency of the association between SII and GCS from Day 1 to Day 3 strengthens the reliability of these findings. It is notable that both correlations and regression coefficients increased slightly over time, potentially indicating a sustained or evolving inflammatory pattern that contributes positively to neurological recovery in the short term.

This study is also unique in its methodological rigor, employing both non-parametric correlation (Spearman's rho) and linear regression to triangulate the predictive relationship.

The strong correlation coefficients ($\rho = 0.817$ and 0.833) and statistically significant beta estimates in both regression models underscore the predictive validity of SII in this context.

However, this interpretation should be approached with caution. The observed positive relationship may be influenced by confounding factors such as the timing of sampling, patient comorbidities, or the nature of the underlying pathology. Furthermore, while GCS is a reliable and widely used tool for assessing neurological status, it has limitations in capturing subtle cognitive or functional impairments.

Future studies that examine the dynamic function of SII in neurological recovery should include bigger populations, longitudinal follow-up, and multi-modal outcome assessments. It would also be beneficial to investigate whether specific thresholds or patterns of change in SII over time correspond with clinically meaningful improvements or deterioration in neurological function.

In summary, the results of this research indicate that the SII could serve as an important biomarker for predicting short-term neurological outcomes, as reflected by GCS scores, in acutely ill patients. These insights open new avenues for integrating inflammatory markers into early prognostic models and tailoring interventions based on immune-inflammatory profiles.

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that the SII functions as a statistically significant and clinically relevant predictor of neurological prognosis, as measured by GCS scores on both Day 1 and Day 3. The results support the integration of SII into routine prognostic assessments in patients with acute brain injury or stroke.

Future to confirm these results, further research involving larger sample sizes and data from multiple centers is advised and examine the mechanisms that connect neurological consequences to systemic inflammation.

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